

School Life Expectancy in the Global Innovation Index

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The variable "School life expectancy, years" represents the total number of years a person, typically a child or adolescent, can expect to spend in the educational system, from primary to tertiary levels, assuming they remain continuously enrolled. This indicator is calculated by considering the entry age and enrollment rates at various educational levels in a country, often integrating data on school completion and dropout rates. School life expectancy does not necessarily imply that all students will complete the anticipated levels of education. Instead, it provides a general estimate of how long, on average, students will remain enrolled. It is used to measure the quality, accessibility, and inclusivity of a country's educational system and serves as an indicator of learning opportunities and human development. Higher indicators of school life expectancy tend to be associated with advanced economies and established educational systems, while lower rates may reflect educational challenges such as barriers to schooling, social and economic inequalities, or the need for child labor. The data covers the period between 2013 and 2022.

School Life Expectancy in the Global Innovation Index in 2022. The data on school life expectancy in the 2022 Global Innovation Index reveals significant global differences in access to and duration of education. These disparities reflect not only the ability of various educational systems to retain students over long periods but also national investments and priorities regarding education and human development. At the top of the list are countries like Australia, New Zealand, and Greece, where school life expectancy exceeds 90%, indicating high access and extended school attendance for most of the student population. In these nations, strong institutional support and inclusive policies are essential for maintaining such a high level, while also fostering a well-educated and competitive workforce. Australia's data, at 100%, shows that, on average, students complete the entire educational trajectory, from primary through tertiary studies, demonstrating a particularly well-developed and supported system. In European countries like Belgium, Sweden, Iceland, and Finland, school life expectancy is around 80-90%, a result that reflects both the well-established tradition of public investment in education and the success of policies aimed at limiting early school dropout. Even in nations like Turkey and Norway, school life expectancy rates remain relatively high, showing that educational support, regardless of different economic or cultural structures, can lead to similar results. Lower on the list, we find countries such as Hong Kong, Germany, Portugal, and South Korea, where school life expectancy ranges between 60% and 70%. These countries, despite having advanced economies and strong infrastructures, present specific challenges, such as high competitiveness and dropout rates at higher education levels, partly due to academic pressure and the conditions for accessing tertiary education. In developing countries such as Brazil, Georgia, and Tunisia, school life expectancy falls below 60%, indicating that many students leave the educational system before completing secondary education. These numbers highlight socio-economic obstacles, such as unequal access and the need for youth labor, which limit school attendance. Educational investments in these areas are often insufficient to support continuous schooling. Finally, in sub-Saharan Africa, including Nigeria, Pakistan, Ethiopia, and Mali, values drop drastically, with school life expectancy below 20 years and, in some cases, under 10 years. These figures point to severe educational underdevelopment, where multiple factors, such as poverty, conflicts, and limited educational resources, prevent continuous access to schooling. This data suggests the urgent need for global support policies aimed at improving educational infrastructure and opportunities in regions that remain isolated from the benefits of quality education.

School Life Expectancy in the Global Innovation Index between 2013 and 2022. The analysis of data on school life expectancy from 2013 to 2022 shows divergent trends globally, reflecting a range of economic, social, and political challenges within educational systems. The school life expectancy

indicator measures the average years of schooling a person is expected to complete in a specific context, revealing the conditions of access to and retention within the educational system. In terms of progress, Burkina Faso and Denmark are examples of countries that have shown significant improvements. Burkina Faso increased its school life expectancy by 7.4 years, from 11.3 to 18.7 years, reflecting a 65.49% increase. This result suggests substantial progress, likely linked to educational investment policies and efforts to improve access in rural areas despite economic challenges. Denmark, with a 28.5-year increase (from 55.5 to 84%), reflects the continuing success of an already robust educational system, supported by inclusive policies and a focus on the quality of higher education. Some middle-income countries, such as Turkey and Morocco, also show notable improvements. School life expectancy in Turkey rose from 59 to 81.5 years (+38.14%), while in Morocco, it increased from 38.1 to 52.9 years (+38.85%). These results indicate significant educational reforms and a growing focus on education as a factor of economic development, although challenges remain to ensure these improvements translate into quality and inclusive education. Conversely, many countries have seen declines in school life expectancy. Italy, for example, saw a significant reduction, dropping from 75.6 to 67 years (-11.38%), indicating a possible rise in dropout rates and structural issues related to the management of educational resources. Countries like France (-15.97%) and the United States (-15.54%) experienced notable declines, possibly due to difficulties in adapting educational systems to the needs of a rapidly evolving global economy and social inequalities that impact uniform access to education. In low-income countries and those with unstable political environments, such as Ethiopia (-48.30%), Mali (-53.85%), and Nigeria (-39.92%), the decline in school life expectancy is particularly dramatic. These data point to persistent difficulties related to factors such as poverty, political instability, and a lack of investment in the education sector. The decline in school life expectancy is concerning, as it often implies that education is not accessible or that structural conditions do not allow children to complete basic education cycles. Asia has shown both improvements and regressions. South Korea, despite its advanced economy, saw a decrease in school life expectancy of 16.46%, suggesting high academic pressures and potential gaps in student support systems. Conversely, countries like the Philippines and Thailand have seen moderate improvements, likely supported by policies to expand educational access.

Conclusions. The average value of school life expectancy decreased for the countries considered between 2013 and 2022, dropping from 58.15 to 55.43 units, corresponding to a change of -4.68%. The top-performing countries are Burkina Faso with +65.49%, Denmark with +51.35%, Morocco with +38.85%, Turkey with +38.14%, and Albania with +30.09%. The lowest-performing countries are Nigeria with -39.92%, Jordan with -43.66%, Ethiopia with -48.30%, Honduras with -49.89%, and Mali with -53.85%.

Performance	Countries	2013	2022	Var Ass	Var Per
Top Performers	Burkina Faso	11,3	18,7	7,4	65,49
	Denmark	55,5	84	28,5	51,35
	Morocco	38,1	52,9	14,8	38,85
	Turkiye	59	81,5	22,5	38,14
	Albania	42,2	54,9	12,7	30,09
Worse Performers	Nigeria	25,8	15,5	-10,3	-39,92
	Jordan	51,3	28,9	-22,4	-43,66
	Ethiopia	26,5	13,7	-12,8	-48,30
	Honduras	44,5	22,3	-22,2	-49,89

	Mali	15,6	7,2	-8,4	-53,85
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References

Leogrande, A., Saponaro, A., Massaro, A., & Galiano, A. M. (2020). A GIS based estimation of quality of life in Italian regions. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)* e-ISSN.

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Impact of Research and Development Expenditures on ESG Model in the Global Economy. Available at SSRN 4414232.

Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., Angelo, L., & Matarrese, M. M. (2023). The intellectual assets in Europe. *International Journal of Entrepreneurship*, 27(2), 1-13.

Magazzino, C., & Leogrande, A. (2021). Subjective well-being in Italian regions: A panel data approach. *Applied econometrics and international development*, 21(1), 1-18.

Leogrande, A., Massaro, A., & Galiano, A. M. (2020). The attractiveness of European research systems. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)*, 4(10), 72-101.

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Role of Political Stability in the Context of ESG Models at World Level. Available at SSRN 4406997.

Leogrande, A. (2023). The Rule of Law in the ESG Framework in the World Economy. Available at

SSRN 4355016.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Role of Government Effectiveness in the Light of ESG Data at Global Level. Available at SSRN 4324938.

Leogrande, A., Massaro, A., & Galiano, A. M. (2020). The impact of R&D investments on corporate performance in European Countries. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)*, 4(7), 186-201.

Leogrande, A., & Costantiello, A. (2023). The Labor Force Participation Rate in the Context of ESG Models at World Level. Available at SSRN 4466452.

Angelo, L., Laureti, L., & Alberto, C. (2022). The Innovation Index in Europe. Available at SSRN 4091597.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., Matarrese, M., & Leogrande, A. (2022). Enterprises Providing ICT Training in Europe. Available at SSRN 4021150.

Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., Leogrande, A., & Matarrese, M. (2021). The Innovation Linkages in Europe. Available at SSRN 3983218.

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Ease of Doing Business in the ESG Framework at World Level. Available at SSRN 4420946.

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Impact of Voice and Accountability in the ESG Framework in a Global Perspective. Available at SSRN 4398483.

Leogrande, A. (2022). Mortality from Cancer in the Italian Regions. *International Web Post*.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2022). Satisfaction with the Environmental Condition in the Italian Regions between 2004 and 2020. Available at SSRN 4061708.